

Photolysis of Diphenylmercury in Zeolites

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There have been a greater emphasis on the study of different causes of pollution of our environment in recent years. Diphenylmercury is one such substance causing a greater pollution of natural water, inhibiting photosynthesis and growth in phytoplankton communities¹. Although there have been several studies on diphenylmercury relating to the mechanism of formation of diphenyl in micellar solution² and formation of benzene in hydrocarbons and alcoholic solvents², no studies have been done yet on a solid heterogeneous media such as zeolites. We report the photolysis of diphenylmercury in type 4A and 13X zeolites. The type 4A zeolite⁴ has the composition $\text{Na}_{12}[\text{AlO}_2]_{12}(\text{SiO}_2)_{12} \cdot 27\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with internal diameter 4 Å and 13X zeolite has the composition $\text{Na}_{86}(\text{AlO}_2)_{86}(\text{SiO}_2)_{106} \cdot 276\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with supercage diameter of 13 Å.

Results and Discussions

Table 1 comprises the results. The degree of photochemical conversion is quite high (15–65%). Since they do not vary much upon a three-fold increase of irradiation time, it may be concluded that recombination of the primary radicals formed (Scheme 1) is by far the dominant reaction.

Photolysis of diphenyl mercury in the solid state and in case of mechanical mixture with 13X, 4A type zeolite does not produce either diphenyl or benzene. Photolysis in the solid state produces black particles and colour of diphenyl mercury becomes yellowish. The weight-loss after irradiation in these cases may be attributed to

some other by-products which could not be identified through GC-MS analysis.

Photolysis on the surface of 4A zeolite and in the cage of 13X zeolite produces diphenyl as well as benzene. However, no further experiment was performed on 4A zeolite under saturated condition. This could give some interesting results as under that condition diphenyl formation could be of negligible amount if at all formed. It is however seen that when the 13X zeolite is fully loaded with diphenylmercury (from the experimental finding maximum of 207.0 mg of diphenylmercury can be introduced in to 1.0 g of 13X zeolite) products obtained are only benzene. However, below the saturation level (when 52.3 mg of diphenylmercury introduced into 1.0 g of zeolite) formation of diphenyl besides benzene is evident. The mechanism of diphenyl and benzene formation is depicted in the scheme below :

In presence of hydrogen donating solvents,

In case of benzene molecule the C–H bond distance is 1.10 Å and C–C bond distance is 1.39 Å. Benzene is a completely flat, symmetrical molecule with carbon-carbon bonds equal and all bond angles are 120°⁵. Calculating on the above basis the dimension of benzene molecule

TABLE 1—PRODUCT YIELDS OF THE PHOTOLYSIS OF DIPHENYLMERCURY IN ZEOLITES

Zeolite type	Amount of zeolite g	Amount of diphenyl mercury mg	Photolysis time h	Diphenyl mg	Benzene mg	Diphenyl mercury left mg
—	—	60.3	1	—	—	39.4
4A	32.5	107.0	1	4.2	3.9	84.8
13X	1.0	52.3	1	0.67	1.7	17.1
13X	1.0	207.0	3.5	—	7.8	78.0

comes to be $\sim 5.9 \text{ \AA}$. For diphenyl this value will be $>11.8 \text{ \AA}$ and $< 13.2 \text{ \AA}$, and for diphenylmercury $> 13 \text{ \AA}$. Taking into consideration the density of type X zeolite as 1.93 g ml^{-1} , average unit cell volume as $15\,516 \text{ \AA}^3$ and each unit cell containing 8 cavities with 13 \AA in diameter⁴, the number of cavities for 1 g of 13X zeolite comes out to be 3×10^{20} . The number of diphenyl mercury molecules in 52.3 mg is 1×10^{20} . So the number of cavities left is $[(3 \times 10^{20}) - (1 \times 10^{20})] = 2 \times 10^{20}$, indicating that there is enough space left for the molecules to move freely. After irradiation the number of diphenylmercury molecules in 17.3 mg of diphenylmercury that is left is 0.33×10^{20} , the number of benzene molecules in 1.7 mg is 0.13×10^{20} and number of diphenyl molecules in 0.67 mg of diphenyl is 2.6×10^{18} . For a benzene molecule of dimension 5.9 \AA it is obvious that two benzene molecules can reside in one cavity. So number of cavities required for benzene molecule is 0.065×10^{20} . Hence total number of cavities required for these products to reside is $[(0.33 \times 10^{20} + 0.065 \times 10^{20} + 0.026 \times 10^{20})] = 0.421 \times 10^{20}$. So number of cavities still left is $[(3 \times 10^{20} - 0.421 \times 10^{20})] = (2.579 \times 10^{20})$. Some of the cavities are occupied by HgO, and some by by-products.

Under saturated condition, the number of diphenylmercury molecules in 207.0 mg of it is 3.51×10^{20} whereas the number of cavities are 3×10^{20} . Moreover, due to its dimension, one cavity is not sufficient for one molecule of

diphenylmercury. This implies that the part of the molecule resides in the channel too. Under this condition it is clear that there is not enough space for phenyl radicals to orient or move to produce diphenyl. After irradiation the number of diphenylmercury molecules in 78.0 mg of it is 1.35×10^{20} and that of benzene molecules in 7.8 mg of it is 0.60×10^{20} . Hence after irradiation, the number of cavities left is $[3 \times 10^{20} - (1.35 \times 10^{20} + 0.30 \times 10^{20})]$, i.e. 1.35×10^{20} , some of the cavities being occupied by HgO and some by by-products.

Experimental

Diphenylmercury (97% pure, E. Merck), benzene (spectrophotometric grade), anhydrous n-pentane (Janseen Chimica), dichloromethane (Riedal Dehaen AG) and zeolites 13X and 4A (Union Carbide) were used.

Sample preparation and photolysis : Prior to use all the zeolites were calcined at 550° for 24 h. Diphenylmercury (1 mg) was solubilised in n-pentane (1 ml), and added to the 20–325 mg depending on the type of zeolite and the mixture was stirred for 7 h. The zeolite after filtration was washed with n-pentane ($3 \times 50 \text{ ml}$). The combined filtrate was analysed by uv spectrophotometry for the diphenylmercury content, and the amount of substrate absorbed by the zeolite sample was then obtained by subtraction. The sample was then vacuum dried and introduced into the quartz cell for photolysis by passing argon over the sample for 15 min to remove oxygen. The photolysis cell was placed

horizontally and rotated continuously during an exposure of 3.5 h at room temperature using quartz filtered light from a high pressure mercury lamp (125 W).

After irradiations the samples were subjected to extraction with CH_2Cl_2 for 5 h in a soxhlet. The solvent was then distilled, the distillate was subjected to uv spectrophotometry to estimate benzene and the residue dissolved in a known amount of benzene which was analysed by gas chromatography using a Hewlett-Packard 5988A instrument. Keeping the system at 60° for an initial period of 2 min after sample injection, the GC-column was heated at a rate of $20^\circ/\text{min}$ upto a final temperature 250° . The products were identified by their mass spectra (X) and by the retention time matching those obtained by injecting authentic samples.

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